

Heterogeneous ring-opening reactions and Knoevenagel condensation reactions with cobalt complexes: Effect of Co^{II} versus Co^{III} states on catalysis

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This work illustrates comparative catalytic performance of two sets of cobalt complexes within a common macrocyclic ligand environment: Co^{II} complexes **1** and **2** versus Co^{III} complexes **3** and **4**. All four cobalt complexes functioned as the heterogeneous catalysts for the ring-opening reactions of assorted epoxides as well as Knoevenagel condensation reactions of assorted aldehydes. Cobalt(II) complexes were noted to be the superior catalysts over cobalt(III) complexes for both types of organic transformations. The observed difference in the catalytic performance of two sets of cobalt complexes has been related to the kinetic differences between Co^{II} versus Co^{III} ions. All four cobalt complexes display high catalytic efficiency and excellent reusability without any apparent loss in the catalytic performance.

Keywords: Cobalt, catalysis, ring-opening reactions, Knoevenagel condensation reactions, heterogeneous catalysis.

Introduction

Ring-opening reactions (RORs) of epoxides with versatile nucleophiles provide an easy access to a variety of fine chemicals¹. The potential list of nucleophiles is essentially endless as assorted reagents could be utilized². In this context, use of amines as the nucleophiles has been particularly significant as such a reaction yields β -amino alcohols, versatile intermediates commonly utilized for the preparation of medicinally and industrially important compounds³. A variety of catalysts have been developed for RORs and include metal salts⁴ and Lewis acid catalyst⁵ whereas recently the focus has been placed on the designer catalysts⁶ including polyoxometallates⁷ and porous framework materials⁸.

Knoevenagel condensation reactions (KCRs) have been extensively explored for the introduction of carbon-carbon bonds in organic synthons⁹. KCRs are typically catalyzed by the Lewis acids; however, assorted reagents and chemicals as well as sophisticated catalysts have also been developed¹⁰. In this context, Lewis acid based heterogeneous catalysts, particularly the reusable ones, are notable due to their high efficiency and ease in product separation¹⁰.

In the context of catalyst design, coordination complexes are noteworthy due to ease in introducing electronic and/or steric demanding substituents in the supporting ligand(s) that

may play significant roles during the catalysis¹¹. In addition, selection of a metal ion in a coordination complex as well as its oxidation state and geometrical preference(s) play critical roles in catalysis¹². However, modulation of such parameters are often difficult to control in the resultant coordination complexes in absence of a set of complexes with nearly identical ligand, although, such a strategy will be useful for the design of a better and efficient catalyst. Recently, we have investigated the effect of oxidation state of cobalt ion as well as electronic substituents present on ligands on the reduction of assorted nitro substrates¹³. Such a feat was only possible by employing a set of macrocyclic ligands providing an identical coordination environment to the central metal ion¹³. In this work, we extend the investigation to two sets of Co complexes within a common macrocyclic ligand environment; Co^{II} complexes **1** and **2** and Co^{III} complexes **3** and **4**; as the efficient catalysts for RORs of assorted epoxides as well as KCRs of assorted aldehydes. We illustrate that the catalytic performance of two sets of cobalt complexes is related to the difference in the oxidation states; Co^{II} versus Co^{III} states.

Experimental

Materials:

The solvents were purified by the standard literature procedures¹⁴. The cobalt complexes **1-4** were synthesized

according to our earlier report¹³.

General procedure for the ring-opening reactions:

In a typical aminolysis reaction, an epoxide substrate (1 mmol) was treated with amine (1.1 mmol) in presence of the cobalt complexes as the catalysts (0.01 mmol) at room temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) and/or gas chromatography (GC). After 7 min, EtOAc (5 mL) was added and the mixture was filtered to remove the catalyst. The crude organic product was purified by the flash column chromatography (60–120 mesh silica gel, EtOAc/hexane, 1:1). The products were analyzed by GC, GC-MS and ^1H NMR spectroscopic techniques.

General procedure for the Knoevenagel condensation reactions:

Aldehydic substrate (1 equiv.) and active-methylene substrate (1.1 equiv.) were dissolved in xylene (5 mL) and solid catalyst (1 mol%) was then added. The reaction mixture was stirred at 100°C for 6 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC and/or GC. The solvent was removed under the reduced pressure and the residue was triturated with ethyl acetate. The catalyst thus separated was collected by filtration and the filtrate was concentrated to afford the crude product. The organic product was purified by column chromatography with 60–120 mesh silica and 1:1 EtOAc/hexanes as the eluent. The products were identified by GC, GC-MS and ^1H NMR spectroscopic techniques.

Physical measurements:

The NMR measurements were done by using a JEOL (400 MHz) instrument. Infrared spectra (with Zn-Se ATR) were recorded by using a Perki-Elmer FTIR spectrum-Two spectrometer. The absorption spectra were recorded by using a Perkin-Elmer Lambda-25 spectrophotometer. The GC studies were performed with a Perkin-Elmer Clarus 580 instrument whereas GC-MS studies were done with a Shimadzu QP 2010 instrument having a RTX-5SIL-MS column.

Results and discussion

This work utilizes two sets of mononuclear cobalt complexes: Co^{II} complexes **1** and **2** and Co^{III} complexes **3** and **4** (Scheme 1). The synthesis and crystal structures of these complexes have already been reported¹³. In both Co^{II} and Co^{III} complexes, a macrocyclic ligand constitutes a N_4 -basal

Scheme 1. Co^{II} (**1** and **2**) and Co^{III} complexes (**3** and **4**) used in this work¹³. In **1** and **2**, O' represents the coordination of an O_{amide} group from an adjacent molecule¹³.

plane where the metal ion is coordinated by two anionic $\text{N}_{\text{amidate}}$ and two neutral N_{amine} donors. The axial ligands are different in two sets of complexes. Co^{II} complexes **1** and **2** exhibit the coordination of O_{amide} atom from an adjacent complex thus producing an one-dimensional zig-zag chain. On the other hand, Co^{III} complexes **3** and **4** display the coordination of a methoxide ion and a water molecule thus resulting in an octahedral geometry. Complexes **2** and **4** further contain electron-withdrawing $-\text{Cl}$ groups on the *o*-phenylene ring of the macrocyclic ligand and are therefore different from the remaining two complexes **1** and **3**. The presence of O_{amide} coordination in complexes **1** and **2** whereas methoxide ion and water ligation in complexes **3** and **4** suggest that such co-ligands could be displaced by other suitable ligands¹⁵. Therefore, such complexes offer noteworthy catalytic possibilities. Moreover, two sets of cobalt complexes differ by the metal's oxidation state. It is well known that Co^{II} complexes are kinetically labile whereas Co^{III} complexes are kinetically inert¹⁶. Therefore, two sets of cobalt complexes provide a significant opportunity to compare their catalysis outcome in view of their different oxidation states. Subsequently, all four cobalt complexes were used as the catalysts for the ring-opening reactions (RORs) as well as Knoevenagel condensation reactions (KCRs).

Ring-opening reactions:

ROR of epoxides with assorted nucleophiles has been a valuable method for the synthesis of significant organic compounds and precursors^{1–3}. In particular, use of a suitable amine provides convenient route for the synthesis of 1,2-amino alcohol, a precursor to many fine and pharmaceuti-

cally important compounds¹⁻³. A variety of catalysts have been developed for RORs; however, reported methods have encountered several limitations such as low yield, moderate chemo- and regio-selectivity, and sensitivity towards assorted functional groups^{1,2}. Several Lewis acids such as metal halides, metal triflates, metal alkoxides, metal amides, and other salts have been employed as the catalysts^{1,2}. However, high catalyst loading and the requirement of elevated temperature and longer reaction time are the major drawbacks^{1,2}. In addition, decomposition of metal salts during the catalysis and degradation of the epoxide and/or products are other serious limitations^{1,2}. Addressing these problems demand identification of inexpensive and recyclable catalysts that could efficiently perform RORs under ambient conditions. In this context, we have utilized cobalt complexes **1-4** as the catalyst for RORs of various epoxides with assorted amines.

In a model reaction, a mixture of styrene oxide (1 equiv.) and aniline (1.1 equiv.) was stirred under solvent-free conditions at room temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) in presence of cobalt complexes **1-4** as the catalyst. Although successful, such a reaction produced the corresponding ring-opened product in varying amounts. At this stage, several control experiments were performed to identify the best reaction conditions (Table 1). No product formation was observed without the use of cobalt complexes **1-4** as the catalyst (Entry 1) that necessitates the requirement of a catalyst in the catalytic reaction. In presence of only 1 mol% of complex **1** as a catalyst, a smooth reaction produced the respective β -amino alcohol in quantitative yield (Entry 2). However, use of $(\text{Et}_4\text{N})_2[\text{CoCl}_4]$ or $\text{Co}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as the catalysts resulted in negligible product formation (Entries 3 and 4). Such a fact explains the importance of supporting ligand in the resultant cobalt complexes for efficiently carrying out the RORs.

The effect of catalyst loading with respect to product yield in RORs of styrene oxide with aniline was also studied using complex **1** as a representative catalyst. For such a purpose, catalyst loading was systematically varied from 0.01 mol% to 0.1 mol% to 1 mol% (Fig. 1). It was found that the reaction time dramatically depended on the catalyst loading. In fact, with 1 mol% catalyst loading, the reaction was completed within 7 min while producing nearly quantitative ring-opened product (>99%). As expected, 0.1 mol% and 0.01 mol% cata-

Table 1. Control experiments for the ring-opening reactions of styrene oxide with aniline^a

Entry	Catalyst	Yield ^b (%)
1	–	0
2	1	100
3	$(\text{Et}_4\text{N})_2[\text{CoCl}_4]$	5
4	$\text{Co}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4

^aCatalyst loading: 1 mol%, styrene oxide: 1 equiv., aniline: 1.1 equiv., Temperature: $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, Time: 7 min. ^bThe products were identified with the gas chromatograph.

lyst loading respectively required 15 and 30 min for quantitative completion. These results are noteworthy and suggest highly active nature of the present cobalt complexes in promoting the RORs. Subsequently, all RORs were carried out using 1 mol% catalyst loading.

To evaluate substrate scope, RORs were carried out employing a few *para*-substituted anilines containing either electron-donating $-\text{OCH}_3$ or electron-withdrawing $-\text{NO}_2$ group (Table 2). Interestingly, *para*-methoxy aniline displayed high

Fig. 1. Time-dependent plots displaying the effect of catalyst loading on product formation for a reaction between styrene oxide and aniline using complex **1** as a catalyst: 1 mol% (pink line), 0.1 mol% (green line), and 0.01 mol% (cyan line).

yield of the ring-opened product when compared to *para*-nitro aniline. Such an observation suggests that electron-donating substituent on aniline has enhanced the nucleophilicity of the substrate that has favored the nucleophilic attack on the epoxide ring (Table 2).

Table 2. Ring-opening reactions of styrene oxide with *para*-substituted anilines using complexes **1-4** as the catalysts^a

Entry	R	Yield ^b (%)			
		1	2	3	4
1	H	100	100	75	78
2	OCH ₃	99	99	62	60
3	NO ₂	41	45	18	19

^aReaction conditions: styrene oxide: 1 equiv., aniline: 1.1 equiv., catalyst loading: 1 mol%, Temperature: 25±1°C, Time: 7 min. ^bThe products were quantified with the gas chromatograph.

The RORs were further extended to cyclohexene oxide, as a representative ring-based epoxide, while utilizing *para*-substituted anilines as the nucleophiles (Table 3). With these substrates, yield of the ring-opened products were again higher for the *para*-substituted anilines having electron-donating -OCH₃ group. Such results are comparable with the RORs of styrene oxide.

Table 3. Ring-opening reactions of cyclohexene oxide with *para*-substituted anilines using catalyst **1-4** as the catalysts^a

Entry	R	Yield ^b (%)			
		1	2	3	4
1	H	100	99	77	84
2	OCH ₃	100	100	74	76
3	NO ₂	12	15	8	4

^aReaction conditions: cyclohexene oxide: 1 equiv.; aniline: 1.1 equiv., catalyst loading: 1 mol%, Temperature: 25±1°C, Time: 7 min. ^bThe products were quantified with the gas chromatograph.

To understand the effect of steric crowding on a substrate, a variety of sterically hindered epoxides such as 2,3-epoxy-2-methylbutane, 2,3-epoxypentane, 1,2-epoxy-3-phenoxypropane, 2-(phenoxy)methyl)oxirane and 2-*tert*-butoxyoxirane were employed (Table 4). Interestingly, a perfect regio-selectivity was observed with exclusive formation of a single regio-product in all cases¹⁷. For example, 2-(phenoxy)methyl)oxirane and 2-*tert*-butoxyoxirane afforded > 97% product formation either with complex **1** or **2** as the catalyst (Entries 1 and 2). Epichlorohydrin is a substrate comprising of an epoxide ring as well as a good leaving group, -Cl. In this case, exclusive formation of the respective β-amino alcohol was noted due to the nucleophilic attack at the terminal carbon atom of the epoxide ring without any trace of the product arising from the nucleophilic displacement of the chlorine atom¹⁷. Thus epichlorohydrin presented a notable example of chemo-selectivity (Entry 3). However, in case of 2,3-epoxy-2-methylbutane (Entry 4) and 2,3-epoxypentane (Entry 5) poor ring-opened products were observed. We reasoned that the presence of steric hindrance due to the alkyl group(s) adjacent to the epoxide ring has potentially hindered the nucleophilic attack by the aniline (Entries 4 and 5)¹⁷.

Table 4. Ring-opening reactions of assorted epoxides with aniline in presence of cobalt complexes **1-4** as the catalysts^a

Entry	Substrate	Yield ^b (%)			
		1	2	3	4
1	2-(Phenoxy)methyl)oxirane	98	99	34	24
2	2- <i>Tert</i> -butoxyoxirane	97	99	27	23
3	Epichlorohydrin	86	90	42	38
4	2,3-Epoxy-2-methylbutane	49	58	15	10
5	2,3-Epoxy-pentane	56	62	26	26

^aCatalyst loading: 1 mol%; epoxide: 1 equiv., aniline: 1.1 equiv., Temperature: 25±1°C, Time: 7 min. ^bThe product were identified with the gas chromatograph.

In literature, RORs have been widely performed using aromatic amines such as aniline; however, comparatively fewer reports are available about the successful use of aliphatic amines¹⁷. After significant results with various substituted anilines; we explored RORs of styrene oxide and cyclohexene oxide using assorted aliphatic amines, such as piperidine, pyrrolidine and cyclohexylamine (Table 5). Satisfyingly, use of piperidine and pyrrolidine as the nucleophile resulted in high yield of the ring-opened products both with

Table 5. Ring-opening reaction of assorted epoxides with aliphatic amines in presence of cobalt complexes **1-4** as the catalysts^a

Entry	Substrate	Amine	Yield ^b (%)			
			1	2	3	4
1	S.O.	Piperidine	92	99	24	29
2	S.O.	Pyrrolidine	87	95	18	25
3	S.O.	Cyclohexylamine	71	92	26	27
4	C.O.	Piperidine	90	97	29	26
5	C.O.	Pyrrolidine	88	94	18	22
6	C.O.	Cyclohexylamine	62	70	22	24

^aCatalyst loading: 1 mol%, epoxide: 1 equiv., amine: 1.1 equiv., Temperature: 25±1°C, Time: 7 min. S.O. and C.O. stand for styrene oxide and cyclohexene oxide, respectively. ^bThe products were identified with the gas chromatograph.

catalysts **1** and **2**. However, with cyclohexylamine, comparatively low conversion was noted when compared to the remaining two aliphatic amines¹⁷. Such a fact again point towards the critical role played by the sterically hindered substrate and/or nucleophile¹⁷.

Knoevenagel condensation reactions:

Knoevenagel condensation reactions (KCRs) have been widely used for the introduction of carbon-carbon double bond in organic molecules^{9,10}. Several catalysts such as assorted acids¹⁸, polymers¹⁹, nanoparticles²⁰, framework materials²¹ and even silica supported materials²² have been reported in the literature. However, Lewis acid metals based catalysts have been particularly successful^{23,24}. After the noteworthy RORs, cobalt complexes **1-4** were used for carrying out KCRs of assorted aldehydes with two different active methylene compounds, ethylcyanoacetate and malononitrile.

Initially, a series of control experiments were performed to ascertain the optimized reaction conditions (Table 6). For such reactions, benzaldehyde was employed as a model substrate along with ethylcyanoacetate in presence of complex **1** as a representative catalyst. Importantly, no reaction was observed when the catalysis was performed without any solvent using complex **1** as a catalyst (Entry 1). Such a fact suggests the crucial role played by the solvent in the catalysis. The use of organic solvents resulted in high conversion that is most probably related to the better mixing of reagents when compared to solvent-free reaction conditions. Assorted solvents resulted in different catalytic performances whereas quantitative product formation was observed in xylene (Entry 2). Fig. 2 illustrates the effect of solvent in KCR of benzal-

Table 6. Control experiments for the Knoevenagel condensation reactions between benzaldehyde and ethylcyanoacetate^a

Entry	Catalyst	Solvent	Temp. (°C)	Yield ^b (%)
1	1	–	25, 100	0, 0
2	1	Dioxane, THF, Benzene, Toluene, MeCN, Xylene	100	0, 25, 30, 84, 42, 100
3	1	Xylene	25, 50, 75	21, 48, 73
4	(Et ₄ N) ₂ [CoCl ₄]	Xylene	100	2
5	Co(OAc) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Xylene	100	4

^aCatalyst loading: 1 mol%, Time: 4 h. ^bProducts were quantified by the gas chromatograph.

Fig. 2. Comparison of Knoevenagel condensation reactions of benzaldehyde with ethylcyanoacetate using complexes **1** and **3** as the catalysts under the solvent-free conditions (●) and using xylene (▲) at 100°C.

dehyde with ethylcyanoacetate using complexes **1** and **3** as the catalysts under the solvent-free conditions as well as in xylene at 100 °C. As can be seen that the presence of xylene as a solvent improved the catalytic performance manifold when compared to solvent-free case both for complexes **1** and **3** as the catalysts. Screening of reaction temperatures

exhibits that the reaction was quantitative at 100°C whereas lower temperatures resulted in poor and/or incomplete reactions (Entries 2 and 3). The use of metal salts, $(\text{Et}_4\text{N})_2[\text{CoCl}_4]$ and $\text{Co}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, as the catalysts resulted in insignificant product formation (Entries 4 and 5). Such a point necessitates the requirement of well-defined cobalt complexes as the catalysts in driving the catalytic reactions successfully.

After establishing the optimized reaction conditions, assorted aldehydic substrates were utilized while using ethylcyanoacetate and malononitrile with all four catalysts (Table 7). As anticipated, benzaldehyde containing electron-withdrawing groups at the *para* position afforded high product yield when compared to the ones with electron-donating substituents (Entries 1-4). The use of naphthaldehyde as an aldehydic substrate provided decent yield of the corresponding product with all four catalysts (Entry 5). Notably, heterocyclic aldehydic substrates provided excellent prod-

uct yields suggesting significant catalysis scope for the present cobalt complexes (Entries 6 and 7). However, aliphatic aldehydes reacted poorly due to their lower reactivity (Entries 8 and 9). Interestingly, corresponding results with malononitrile were quite impressive as most of the catalytic reactions were found to complete within 10 min (Entries 10-18). In fact, with malononitrile, nearly 50% conversion was observed within the first 5 min of the reaction with only 1 mol% catalyst loading. These results are noteworthy and suggest very high catalytic performance of the present cobalt complexes as the heterogeneous catalysts.

Mechanistically, both RORs and KCRs are known to be promoted by the activation of a substrate (epoxide or aldehyde) by a Lewis acidic metal followed by the attack of a nucleophile^{9,11}. In the present case, we propose that a substrate first replaces co-ligands (O_{amide} in **1** and **2** or H_2O in **3** and **4**) bound to the cobalt ion during the activation step. The oxidation state of cobalt ion (+2 versus +3) in these com-

Table 7. Knoevenagel condensation reactions of assorted aldehydic substrates using ethylcyanoacetate and malononitrile using cobalt complexes **1-4** as the catalysts^a

Entry	R	R ₁	R ₂	Yield ^b (%)			
				1	2	3	4
1	C ₆ H ₅	CO ₂ Et	CN	87	99	64	72
2	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₅	CO ₂ Et	CN	83	93	68	70
3	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	CO ₂ Et	CN	82	94	61	76
4	4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	CO ₂ Et	CN	76	86	58	62
5	Napthalen-2-yl	CO ₂ Et	CN	62	73	46	53
6	Furan-2-yl	CO ₂ Et	CN	81	96	67	71
7	Thiophen-2-yl	CO ₂ Et	CN	84	95	60	70
8	Me or Et	CO ₂ Et	CN	0	0	0	0
9	ClCH ₂	CO ₂ Et	CN	10	13	5	4
10 ^c	C ₆ H ₅	CN	CN	100	100	59	56
11 ^c	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₅	CN	CN	96	100	54	42
12 ^c	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	CN	CN	94	99	51	42
13 ^c	4-OMeC ₆ H ₄	CN	CN	95	98	50	47
14 ^c	Napthalen-2-yl	CN	CN	86	97	49	44
15 ^c	Furan-2-yl	CN	CN	97	99	0	0
16 ^c	Thiophen-2-yl	CN	CN	88	98	42	36
17 ^c	Me or Et	CN	CN	0	0	0	0
18 ^c	ClCH ₂	CN	CN	13	22	10	4

^aCatalyst loading: 1 mol%, Solvent: xylene; Time: 4 h. ^bProducts were quantified by the gas chromatograph. ^cTime: 7 min.

plexes plays a critical role at this stage and actually controls the catalytic outcome (*vide infra*).

Reusability experiments:

Reusability and recyclability of a catalyst are important factors in view of wider application potentials^{23,24}. In this aspect, heterogeneous catalysts are considered better compared to the homogeneous ones¹². In heterogeneous catalysis, a catalyst can be easily recovered from the reaction mixture by simple filtration¹². Such a strategy further provides a significant scope to evaluate the recyclability of a catalyst as well as provide an option to characterize a recovered catalyst¹². Taking advantage of heterogeneous nature of catalysis, we investigated the reusability of the present cobalt complexes both in the RORs of styrene oxide with aniline and KCRs of benzaldehyde with malononitrile. For such reactions, complex **1** was selected as a representative catalyst. Separation of any of the catalysts was realized by the addition of ethyl acetate to the reaction mixture followed by filtration of the catalyst and vacuum drying. It is important to mention that no further purification and/or regeneration of a catalyst was carried out. As can be seen from Fig. 3, recovered catalyst **1** was reused for six consecutive cycles without any regeneration or purification. In all cases, over >99% product formation was achieved that illustrates robustness as well as high catalytic performance of catalyst **1** (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Recycling experiments for six cycles using complex **1** as a catalyst for (a) ring-opening reaction of styrene oxide with aniline (green bars) and (b) Knoevenagel condensation reaction of benzaldehyde with malononitrile (blue bars).

To further illustrate the catalytic efficiency of complex **1** as a catalyst, an interesting experiment was performed. In

this experiment, separate batches of styrene oxide and aniline were added to a flask containing fixed quantity of 1-mol% of complex **1** as a catalyst (Fig. 4). As can be seen from Fig. 4, nearly quantitative ring-opened products were achieved for all four catalytic cycles. This experiment strongly justifies highly efficient and robust nature of the present catalysts in promoting the RORs.

Fig. 4. Reusability plot, for four consecutive catalytic cycles, for a reaction between styrene oxide and aniline using complex **1** as a catalyst.

To confirm that the catalytically active species (e.g. cobalt ion) is not leached out during course of the reaction, 'filtration test' was performed using complex **1** as a representative catalyst during a reaction between styrene oxide and aniline. Herein, complex **1** was removed by filtration during the course of the reaction whereas the reaction was allowed to continue. Notably, as soon as the catalyst was removed from the reaction mixture, the reaction was completely ceased. However, re-addition of the same catalyst to the reaction mixture resumed the reaction which ultimately produced the desired ring-opened product in nearly quantitative yield. This simple filtration test conclusively infers that the present cobalt complexes are indeed acting as the true heterogeneous catalysts during the catalytic reactions.

Comparison of catalysis:

A comparison of catalysis results immediately suggest a significant difference between two sets of cobalt complexes: Co^{II} complexes **1** and **2** versus Co^{III} complexes **3** and **4**. It is clearly noticeable that the Co^{II} complexes **1** and **2** are much superior catalysts when compared to Co^{III} complexes **3** and **4**. We propose that the difference in the catalytic performance of two sets of complexes is related to the kinetically labileness

Fig. 5. (a) Ring-opening reaction of styrene oxide with aniline in presence of complex **1** as a catalyst (green spheres); (b) **1** was filtered off after 4 min leading to the termination of catalytic reaction (cyan spheres); (c) **1** was re-added after 1 min causing commencement of the reaction (magenta spheres) and leading to completeness of the reaction.

of Co^{II} complexes versus kinetically inertness of Co^{III} complexes¹⁶. As two sets of complexes primarily differ by the oxidation state of the cobalt ion, following reasoning appears reasonable. It is important to note that both Co^{II} and Co^{III} ions are also Lewis acidic in nature whereas the Lewis acidity of a Co^{III} ion is higher than that of Co^{II} ion^{23,24}. Both RORs and KCRs are known to be catalyzed by Lewis acidic metals^{9,11}. As a result, Co^{III} complexes **3** and **4**, despite having a kinetically inert Co^{III} ion and not able to fully support the exchange of ligated co-ligands, are able to illustrate decent catalytic performance. The present results are noteworthy for the design of better catalysts for challenging organic transformations and illustrate that both Lewis acidity of a catalytic metal and kinetic parameters are significant criteria that potentially control the catalysis outcome.

Conclusions

This work has presented comparative catalytic performance of two sets of cobalt complexes: Co^{II} complexes **1** and **2** versus Co^{III} complexes **3** and **4**. Both sets of cobalt complexes acted as the heterogeneous catalysts for ring-opening reactions of assorted epoxides as well as Knoevenagel condensation reactions of assorted aldehydes. Cobalt(II) complexes were found to be the superior catalysts over cobalt(III) complexes for both types of organic transformations. Such a stark difference in the catalytic performance of two sets of cobalt complexes has been related to the kinetic differences between Co^{II} versus Co^{III} ions. High cata-

lytic efficiency and excellent reusability of the present cobalt complexes suggest their noteworthy applications in other challenging organic transformations.

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